
PER-COUNTRY CAPS AND THE CONCENTRATION OF INTERGENERATIONAL HARM: A MICROSIMULATION OF AGE-OUT DYNAMICS IN THE UNITED STATES EMPLOYMENT-BASED IMMIGRATION SYSTEM

A PREPRINT

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November 30, 2025

ABSTRACT

The U.S. employment-based (EB) immigration system operates under two binding statutory constraints: a fixed annual limit of 140,000 visas and a 7% per-country cap. Together, these rules generate backlogs exceeding 1.8 million applicants and produce wait times that vary by decades across nationalities. These extended delays carry acute implications for dependent children, who lose eligibility for derivative status at age 21. Although prior research has estimated the backlog's scale and documented its unequal distribution, it has not produced a unified, petitioner-level model capable of capturing the queue's temporal evolution, isolating the specific contribution of the per-country cap, and quantifying child age-out risk under alternative policy regimes. This study addresses these gaps by developing a discrete-event microsimulation of the EB immigration system that reconstructs the queue at the petitioner level. The model integrates EB visa petitions from FY2013–FY2024, assigns dependents using nationality-specific demographic profiles, and simulates visa allocations incorporating per-country ceilings, their statutory exceptions, inter-category spillovers, and family-based spillover provisions. Calibration to the June 2025 USCIS backlog yields close agreement with administrative data, reproducing the total backlog within 1.6% and the India EB-2/EB-3 queues within 0.8%. The model is then projected through FY2035 under two scenarios: the current capped system and an uncapped counterfactual that removes only the per-country limit. Across the projection period, age-outs rise from 3,721 under uncapped allocation to 62,764 under capped allocation, an increase of 59,043. In the capped scenario, Indian children account for 98.8% of all age-outs, compared to 36.1% in the uncapped scenario. The findings provide the first integrated estimate of how per-country limits dynamically magnify and concentrate intergenerational exclusion within the U.S. EB immigration system.

Keywords Employment-based immigration · per-country limitations · backlog · child age-out · family separation · microsimulation

1 Introduction

1.1 The Crisis of Indefinite Wait Times

The U.S. employment-based (EB) immigration system faces a backlog of more than 1.8 million foreign nationals awaiting permanent residency (Bier, 2023). Crucially, this burden is distributed unequally. Under the 7% per-country cap established by the Immigration Act of 1990, nationals from high-demand countries, most notably India and China, encounter severe distortions in visa availability (Ennis, 2024). Indian nationals, for example, constitute a substantial share of high-skilled applicants but are statutorily limited to only a small fraction of annual EB visa numbers. As a result, two identically qualified professionals applying on the same day can face radically different processing timelines solely because of their country of birth, with projected waits for Indian applicants in the EB-2 category extending beyond 195 years under current rules (Kandel, 2020).

These prolonged backlogs produce significant intergenerational consequences. U.S. immigration law limits derivative eligibility to unmarried children under the age of 21; once a child reaches this threshold, they “age out” of the application, losing both dependent status and lawful presence even if their parent’s petition remains pending (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.a). Each additional year of delay thus generates a new cohort of “Documented Dreamers”—children raised and educated in the United States who face sudden vulnerability at adulthood despite long-term legal residency during their formative years. Advocacy groups estimate that more than 200,000 Documented Dreamers are in the United States (American Immigration Council, 2024).

1.2 Existing Gaps and Research Goals

Existing scholarship has documented the scale of the green card backlog and qualitatively described its disparate impact. However, prior studies generally fail to (1) dynamically model how backlogs evolve as cohorts age, (2) isolate the specific causal contribution of the per-country cap versus the fixed annual supply, or (3) project future age-out incidence under alternative policy scenarios.

To address these deficiencies, this study develops a dynamic microsimulation analysis that explicitly links policy structure to demographic outcomes. We aim to quantify the mechanisms that existing research has only described conceptually. Specifically, we investigate how the imposition of the 7% per-country cap alters the incidence of child age-outs compared to a first-in-first-out (FIFO) baseline. We hypothesize that the per-country cap does not merely redistribute wait times but fundamentally alters the demographic composition of the beneficiary pool, concentrating extended delays, and consequently, age-outs, among specific high-demand nationalities.

By simulating these dynamics, we seek to resolve three empirical questions: the aggregate differential in child age-outs between capped and uncapped regimes; the resulting shift in the nationality distribution of the backlog; and the intensity with which family separation risks are concentrated within specific preference categories and nationalities.

1.3 Methodological Innovation

The study investigates these questions using a discrete event microsimulation model that reconstructs the employment-based green card queue at the individual petitioner level. The simulation is initialized with historical petition microdata (FY2013–FY2024) and calibrated to match USCIS administrative backlog data as of June 2025. It tracks individual principal applicants through the complete immigration lifecycle, from queue entry to eventual visa allocation or queue exit.

Simultaneously, the model generates and tracks dependent spouses and children for each principal applicant based on nationality-specific demographic profiles derived from IPUMS data (Ruggles et al., 2025). The model projects these dynamics over a ten-year horizon (FY2025–FY2035) under two scenarios: a capped regime reflecting the current 7% per-country cap, and an uncapped counterfactual. This comparative design isolates the specific causal effect of the per-country cap on wait times and intergenerational outcomes, independent of aggregate visa supply constraints.

1.4 Contribution to the Literature

This paper advances immigration policy research in three distinct ways. First, it provides the first rigorous quantification of child age-out risks. While past scholarship offers static estimates of the “at-risk” population, this study dynamically projects actual age-out incidence, transforming a speculative concern into a measurable policy outcome. Second, it establishes a unified legal-demographic simulation framework. By integrating statutory rules with demographic transition modeling, we offer a transferable architecture for analyzing how administrative constraints shape outcomes, a framework applicable to family-based immigration and other queue-dependent policy domains. Finally, we provide an empirical measurement of policy-induced inequality. By disentangling the per-country cap from the aggregate visa limit, we quantify the specific magnitude of disparity attributable to country-of-origin discrimination, offering a precise evidence base for legislative debate.

2 Background and Literature Review

2.1 The Statutory Architecture of Backlogs

The U.S. employment-based immigration system operates under a binding statutory framework that generates the backlog dynamics analyzed in this study. The foundational constraint is the aggregate annual cap of 140,000 employment-based (EB) visas per fiscal year, inclusive of all derivative beneficiaries (spouses and dependent children) (U.S.

Department of State, n.d.a). While this ceiling is technically fixed, the statute allows for “spillover” from the family-based preferences, where unutilized family-sponsored visas from the prior fiscal year are added to the employment-based pool (Kandel et al., 2022). In FY2024, for example, approximately 27,000 additional visas spilled over, raising the effective employment-based limit to roughly 167,000 (U.S. Department of State, n.d.b).

EB visas are distributed hierarchically across five preference categories. EB-1 (priority workers), EB-2 (advanced degree professionals), and EB-3 (skilled workers) are each allocated 28.6% of the worldwide limit (approximately 40,040 visas plus spillover), while EB-4 and EB-5 each receive 7.1% (approximately 9,940). Crucially, the current statute includes a vertical spillover sequence: unused EB-4/EB-5 numbers flow “up” to EB-1; unused EB-1 numbers flow “down” to EB-2; and unused EB-2 numbers flow to EB-3 (Kandel et al., 2022).

Superimposed on these category limits is the 7% per-country cap. No single country of origin may receive more than 7% of the total visas available in a fiscal year. However, there is a critical exception: if the number of visas available in a specific category exceeds the number of qualified applicants (while considering the 7% per-country limit) in a given fiscal quarter, the per-country cap is waived for that category. This mechanism allows high-demand countries to access “leftover” visas that would otherwise go unused, but only after demand from the rest of the world has been satisfied (U.S. Department of State, n.d.c).

Despite these spillover and waiver mechanisms, the structural bottleneck remains severely limiting. For high-demand nations, specifically India and China, the cap becomes a binding constraint long before the aggregate category limit is reached (U.S. Department of State, 2025). This creates a bifurcated system: a “General Queue” that clears relatively quickly, and country-specific “Oversubscribed Queues” where wait times are determined not simply by global supply, but by the 7% fractional limit. The result is a massive concentration of the backlog.

As of 2023, the total employment-based backlog exceeded 1.8 million individuals. Over 1.1 million are Indian nationals, primarily concentrated in the EB-2 and EB-3 categories (Bier, 2023).

2.2 The Mechanics of Intergenerational Status Loss

The interaction between multi-decade wait times and derivative eligibility rules creates the humanitarian consequence of “aging out.” A child’s derivative status is contingent upon being unmarried and under 21 years of age. While the Child Status Protection Act (CSPA) of 2002 allows for the subtraction of administrative processing time from a child’s biological age, it does not toll age during the years (or decades) spent waiting for a visa number to become available (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.a). Consequently, children in oversubscribed queues effectively race their biological clock against the statutory processing rate.

When a child reaches age 21 prior to visa availability, they lose eligibility for derivative adjustment of status and typically face three divergent trajectories. First, some secure independent F-1 student status, a pathway that imposes international tuition rates, bars access to federal financial aid (Broder and Kmec, 2025), and offers only temporary relief that expires upon or soon after degree completion (U.S. Department of State, n.d.d). Second, others attempt to transition to H-1B status, but face low lottery acceptance rates and the consequence of restarting the immigration queue from the end of the line (Malik and Saada, 2025). Third, those unable to secure independent status must depart the United States for countries they may barely remember, or remain without legal status, risking deportation and permanent bars on future reentry (Legal Information Institute, n.d.).

2.3 Limitations of Existing Approaches

Given the severity of outcomes for aged-out children, accurate quantification of the at-risk population is essential for informed policymaking. However, despite the growing policy salience of these dynamics, the existing literature on child age-outs is constrained by three methodological limitations that obscure the true scale and mechanism of the crisis.

First, current research relies primarily on static, cross-sectional analysis. Recent estimates suggest that approximately 275,000 immigrant children reside in households with temporary visas or pending employment-based petitions (Moriarty, 2024). However, this figure reflects a snapshot of children currently in the system, not a projection of those who will ultimately lose status. While Bier (2020) estimates that 100,000 children are “at risk” of family separation, the figure is derived from static, aggregate administrative counts rather than a model of how individuals move through the queue over time. Static calculations offer useful descriptive benchmarks, but they cannot capture how wait times evolve or how age-out risk compounds across multiple cohorts. In contrast, dynamic microsimulation enables more precise estimates of future age-outs and supports extrapolation over longer time horizons, generating a fuller picture of how policy constraints shape intergenerational outcomes.

Second, the literature has failed to causally isolate the impact of the per-country cap from the aggregate visa quota. The U.S. system operates under two simultaneous binding constraints: the global limit of 140,000 visas and the 7% per-country limit. Extended wait times for certain nationals are the compound result of both factors. Prior studies typically conflate these effects, leaving policymakers unable to apportion causality. For instance, if an applicant faces a multi-decade delay, existing models cannot determine what proportion of that wait is independently attributable to the global visa shortage versus the country-specific cap. No prior study has simulated a dynamic, counterfactual “uncapped” regime to empirically disentangle these competing constraints.

Third, there is a lack of rigorous disaggregated distributional analysis. While aggregate estimates of the “at-risk” population exist, the specific distribution of projected age-outs across nationalities and preference categories remains unquantified. Existing attempts to disaggregate these risks (e.g., Bier, 2020) are constrained by methodological opacity, relying on undisclosed “author’s calculations” derived from aggregate data rather than reproducible microsimulation. Without a transparent, petitioner-level reconstruction of the queue, these estimates cannot capture the complex interplay of category spillovers and demographic variation. Consequently, whether age-outs are distributed broadly across the applicant pool or concentrated almost entirely within specific nationality-category cells remains an open empirical question.

This study overcomes these methodological barriers by implementing a dynamic microsimulation framework that directly resolves each limitation. First, by reconstructing the queue at the individual petitioner level, we replace static snapshots with longitudinal tracking, allowing us to measure the precise interaction between biological aging and administrative processing for every dependent child. Second, by simulating a capped (status quo) regime against an uncapped (counterfactual) regime, we rigorously disentangle the marginal effect of the 7% per-country cap from the baseline aggregate visa constraint, resolving the causal ambiguity present in prior literature. Finally, we replace opaque aggregate estimates with a transparent, fully disaggregated analysis of age-out incidence, quantifying exactly how these intergenerational burdens are concentrated across specific nationalities and employment-based preference categories.

3 Conceptual Framework

3.1 Causal Mechanism

This study hypothesizes that the 7% per-country cap generates substantially more child age-outs than an uncapped regime through a three-stage causal mechanism that systematically disadvantages high-demand nationalities.

Stage 1: Per-Country Caps Create Nationality-Skewed Backlogs The per-country cap restricts each nationality to no more than 7% of the annual allocation within an EB category, regardless of underlying demand. This constraint creates a structural supply–demand imbalance: for instance, Indian nationals constitute roughly 86% of the EB-2 backlog, yet are held to a 7% share of annual EB-2 issuance (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Each year, the inflow of Indian EB-2 petitions massively exceeds the outflow permitted by the cap, and the difference accumulates as a nationality-specific backlog. Any nationality whose demand surpasses 7% of the category’s annual supply experiences this structural bottleneck. In this way, the per-country limit imposes a multiplicative effect on backlog growth, magnifying national-origin disparities far beyond what would occur under an uncapped system.

Stage 2: Nationality-Skewed Backlogs Produce Highly Unequal Wait Times As nationality-specific queues grow, workers from high-demand countries face substantially longer waits than similarly situated applicants from lower-demand countries. The result is a set of lengthened queues and wait times that would not emerge under an uncapped allocation regime.

Stage 3: Extended Wait Times Generate Disproportionate Child Age-Outs A dependent child remains eligible for derivative status only if the parent receives permanent residence before the child turns 21 (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.a). When wait times for certain nationalities exceed decades, as they do under the capped regime, the probability of aging out increases substantially for entire cohorts. Thus, the per-country cap increases age-out risk by manufacturing extreme, nationality-specific delays that push many children past the statutory age threshold.

Consequently, the cap-based system produces not only more age-outs in aggregate than an uncapped regime, but also concentrates these harms almost exclusively among petitioners from high-demand nationalities. This study’s modeling framework is designed to isolate and quantify this causal structure.

4 Methods

4.1 Research Design Overview

The research design proceeds in three phases: synthetic reconstruction, calibration, and projection.

First, we reconstruct the modern backlog by initializing an empty queue in FY2013 and feeding it historical I-140 petition filing data (FY2013–FY2024) disaggregated by nationality and EB category. Each principal applicant is probabilistically assigned family dependents (spouse and children) and child ages based on nationality-specific demographic profiles derived from IPUMS American Community Survey (ACS) data. These agents proceed through the statutory visa allocation system, subject to actual historical visa limits, per-country caps (7%), and category cascades.

Second, the model is calibrated and validated against administrative benchmarks. Queue exit rates, representing emigration, death, or withdrawals, are tuned to match the simulation’s terminal state against the actual USCIS backlog inventory as of June 2025. The calibrated model achieves high precision, reproducing the aggregate backlog within 1.6% and the critical India EB-2/EB-3 sub-populations to within 0.8% of administrative totals.

Third, we extend the simulation into a projection period (FY2025–FY2035) to compare two policy scenarios:

- **Baseline (Capped):** Maintains the current 7% per-country cap and statutory allocation rules.
- **Counterfactual (Uncapped):** Removes the per-country cap while retaining all other statutory limits.

By holding petition inflows, demographics, and total visa supply constant across scenarios, the model isolates the specific causal effect of the per-country cap mechanism on wait times and, consequently, on the probability that dependent children reach age 21 prior to visa allocation.

4.2 Parameter Calibration

4.2.1 Annual Volumes and Pathway Classification: Synthetic Backlog Construction and Forward Projection

The employment-based immigration system processes immigrant petitions across multiple statutory preference levels (EB-1 through EB-5), each containing distinct subcategories that operate through different petition forms (Kandel et al., 2022). To model annual petition flows with empirical accuracy, this study employs a two-phase temporal approach: (1) synthetic backlog reconstruction using historical petition data from fiscal years 2013–2024, and (2) forward projection from fiscal year 2024 onward using FY2024 as a constant baseline.

All employment-based petition and backlog data are derived from two primary sources: the U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services (USCIS) public reports and databases, and the U.S. Department of State Visa Office records. Specifically, we extracted I-140, I-360, and I-526 petition approval volumes from USCIS quarterly statistical reports (FY2013–FY2024) and backlog inventory counts from the June 2025 USCIS administrative data release (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b). Visa allocation history and annual allocation methodology were obtained from the Department of State’s Report of the Visa Office (U.S. Department of State, n.d.b).

Two-Phase Modeling Architecture Phase 1: Synthetic Backlog Initialization (FY2013–FY2024)

The simulation begins by reconstructing the visa allocation queue as it existed at the end of fiscal year 2024. To accurately model the biological aging of dependent children, the simulation employs a synthetic backlog reconstruction approach. Rather than initializing with a static snapshot of the current queue (which lacks historical data on child entry ages), we iteratively process historical petition approval volumes from FY2013–FY2024. This longitudinal reconstruction allows the model to assign correct “biological clocks” to dependents based on their specific year of entry, ensuring that the age-out risk profile of the initial backlog reflects the true accumulation of wait time.

The reconstruction proceeds as follows:

- **Initialization (FY2013):** The simulation initializes with empty queues, treating fiscal year 2013 as the baseline year prior to backlog accumulation.
- **Annual Historical Injection (FY2013–FY2024):** For each fiscal year from 2013 through 2024, the model adds workers to the visa allocation queue based on actual historical I-140, I-360, and I-526 petition approval data extracted from USCIS annual data.
- **Concurrent Visa Processing:** Simultaneously, the model allocates employment-based visas according to historical annual visa pools, which varied depending on family-based spillover availability in each fiscal year. The visa allocation engine processes queued workers according to statutory per-country caps and category-based allocation rules.

- **Queue Accumulation:** By the end of fiscal year 2024, the synthetic backlog generates a fully populated state that captures not only the correct volume of pending applicants but also their accumulated demographic history. Unlike a static snapshot, this reconstructed queue contains a heterogeneous population of dependent children with varying “biological runways,” some who entered as infants in 2013 and are now teenagers, and others who arrived recently. This establishes a calibrated starting point for the forward projection of child age-outs.

Phase 2: Forward Projection (FY2025 and Beyond)

Beginning in fiscal year 2024, the simulation transitions to a constant inflow assumption, where annual petition volumes and demographic parameters are held fixed at their FY2024 empirical levels.

I-140 Pathways: EB-1, EB-2, and EB-3 Categories The EB-1, EB-2, and EB-3 preference categories encompass nine distinct I-140 petition pathways. The model extracts FY2024 petition receipt volumes from USCIS quarterly statistical reports (Form I-140, Immigrant Petition for Alien Workers) as follows:

Table 1: FY2024 I-140 Petition Volumes by Pathway

Pathway	EB Category	FY2024 Petitions
E11	EB-1	12,322
E12	EB-1	4,620
E13	EB-1	14,532
E21	EB-2	46,816
NIW	EB-2	27,611
E31	EB-3	20,726
E32	EB-3	22,863
EW3	EB-3	10,194
Subtotal		159,684

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

I-360 Pathways: EB-4 Special Immigrants The EB-4 category presents unique data extraction challenges because Form I-360 (Petition for Amerasian, Widow(er), or Special Immigrant) serves both employment-based and family-based immigration pathways. The model employs a two-step disaggregation process to isolate employment-based EB-4 demand:

Step 1: Extract SIJS Petition Volume

The model first obtains Special Immigrant Juveniles (SIJS) petition counts directly from USCIS quarterly performance data, which reports SIJS as a distinct subcategory. SIJS petitioners are unaccompanied minors who have been abused, neglected, or abandoned, and consequently exhibit drastically different spousal accompaniment rates and dependent child rates.

Step 2: Extract Non-SIJS EB-4 Petition Volume

The model separately extracts I-360 petition counts for all other employment-based special immigrant classifications, excluding both SIJS and family-based I-360 petitions (such as VAWA self-petitions for abused family members). These residual EB-4 petitions include designated special immigrants, the most prominent of whom are religious workers.

This two-pathway disaggregation ensures that SIJS petitioners, who as minor children themselves have fundamentally different derivative beneficiary patterns, are modeled separately from adult-petitioned EB-4 pathways that follow conventional spouse and child accompaniment rates.

Table 2: FY2024 EB-4 Petition Volumes

Pathway	FY2024 Receipts
SIJS	70,859
Other EB-4	15,164
EB-4 Total	86,023

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

I-526 Pathway: EB-5 Immigrant Investors For the EB-5 category, the model utilizes Form I-526 petition receipts (Immigrant Petition by Alien Investor) for fiscal year 2024:

Table 3: FY2024 EB-5 Petition Volumes

Pathway	EB Category	FY2024 Petitions
EB-5	EB-5	5,385

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Aggregate Annual Inflow and Structural Imbalance The combined annual queue entry volume across all pathways totals 251,101 approved petitions per year. This reflects the gross inflow of immigrants entering the visa allocation queue.

The total approved petition volume (251,101), even without accounting for derivative beneficiaries, substantially exceeds the annual visa supply (167,394 visas comprising 140,000 base allocation plus 27,394 family-based spillover based on FY2024 data). This imbalance generates queue accumulation and backlog formation, which is a structural feature of the current U.S. employment-based immigration system.

4.2.2 Nationality Distributions by Pathway

EB-1 through EB-3 Pathways: Complete Historical I-140 Microdata For EB-1, EB-2, and EB-3 pathways, the model utilizes USCIS I-140 quarterly statistical reports for fiscal years 2013–2024. These reports provide annual approval counts disaggregated by specific classification (E11, E12, E13, E21, E31, E32, EW3) and nationality. This granularity enables the construction of exact pathway-specific nationality distributions for the synthetic backlog reconstruction period (FY2013–FY2024).

The model explicitly tracks the five origin countries for which USCIS reports comprehensive data—India, China, Philippines, Brazil, and South Korea—while aggregating all remaining nations into an “Other” category. For each fiscal year and sub-category, the model computes a specific nationality distribution based on historical approval shares. Crucially, these granular sub-category flows are then aggregated up to their respective statutory preference levels (EB-1, EB-2, and EB-3) to model the final inflow of principal applicants into the visa allocation queue.

Table 4: EB-1 Pathway Nationality Distributions

Nationality	E11 (%)	E12 (%)	E13 (%)
China	33.9	38.6	6.3
India	19.7	29.6	43.1
Brazil	4.3	1.9	5.8
South Korea	1.8	2.6	2.9
Philippines	0.2	0.2	0.8
Other	40.1	27.1	41.0

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Table 5: EB-2 Pathway Nationality Distributions

Nationality	E21 (%)	NIW (%)
India	71.0	12.9
China	13.3	20.5
Other	13.7	53.3
Brazil	0.7	8.9
South Korea	1.0	4.2
Philippines	0.3	0.2

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Table 6: EB-3 Pathway Nationality Distributions

Nationality	E31 (%)	E32 (%)	EW3 (%)
Philippines	41.0	5.4	7.4
Other	40.3	26.0	76.4
India	10.4	36.1	0.2
China	2.5	28.0	3.3
South Korea	3.4	3.1	5.0
Brazil	2.4	1.5	7.7

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

EB-4 and EB-5 Pathways: Data Constraints and Proxy Calibration By contrast, EB-4 and EB-5 pathways lack equally granular, longitudinal petition-level nationality data. USCIS did not publish disaggregated nationality distributions for I-360 (EB-4) and I-526 (EB-5) filings by subcategory and country of origin over 2013–2024.

The model therefore adopts proxy-based calibration strategies tailored to each pathway:

- **SIJS (Special Immigrant Juvenile Status, EB-4):** The model utilizes historical nationality distributions of unaccompanied minors in U.S. immigration court proceedings (FY2009–FY2023) (Galli and Padilla, 2025). Given that SIJS functions as a form of immigration relief for unaccompanied children in the U.S., the demographic composition of minors in these proceedings serves as a robust proxy for petition inflows in this sub-category.
- **Other EB-4 (Religious Workers and Other Special Immigrants):** The “Other EB-4” composite includes special immigrants, the most prominent of whom (excluding SIJS) are religious workers (Wilson, 2024). Because disaggregated I-360 nationality data is not published for these subgroups, the model uses FY2024 R-1 nonimmigrant religious worker visa issuance nationality distributions as a proxy, justified by the fact that religious workers constitute the largest identifiable EB-4 subcategory after SIJS.
- **EB-5 (Immigrant Investors):** USCIS does not routinely report I-526 nationality distributions for petition filings. Instead, the model uses FY2024 EB-5 immigrant visa issuance nationality distributions as a proxy for investor petition composition. This captures the dominant investor origins, with the caveat that issuance data may underrepresent countries constrained by the 7% per country cap.

For the synthetic backlog phase (FY2013–FY2024), the model applies the FY2024 EB-4 and EB-5 nationality distributions retrospectively, imposing an assumption of stable nationality composition for these categories.

Table 7: EB-4 Pathway Nationality Distributions

Nationality	SIJS (%)	Other EB-4 (%)
Other	98.8	88.5
India	0.6	6.5
China	0.2	0.4
Philippines	0.0	1.6
South Korea	0.0	1.5
Brazil	0.0	1.5

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b); U.S. Department of State, Report of the Visa Office (U.S. Department of State, n.d.b).

Table 8: EB-5 Pathway Nationality Distributions

Nationality	EB-5 (%)
China	64.8
Other	22.4
India	9.6
South Korea	2.2
Brazil	1.1
Philippines	0.1

Source: U.S. Department of State, Report of the Visa Office (U.S. Department of State, n.d.b).

4.2.3 Spouse Presence and Dependent Children

Employment-based visa beneficiaries may bring spouses and unmarried children under age 21 as derivative beneficiaries (Kandel et al., 2022). The number of dependent children at risk of aging out depends jointly on two factors: the probability that a worker has an accompanying spouse (a prerequisite for child derivation in the simulation), and the number and ages of children conditional on spouse presence.

Data Source: IPUMS American Community Survey The model calibrates spouse presence, children count, and child entry age using microdata from the IPUMS American Community Survey (ACS) for fiscal years 2018–2023 (pooled) (Ruggles et al., 2025). The ACS provides nationally representative data on the U.S. population, including detailed information on foreign-born residents, household composition, marital status, and children.

The target population for calibration is foreign-born workers aged 25–65 residing in U.S. households with valid employment status. This population closely approximates the demographic profile of employment-based visa beneficiaries: working-age immigrants with labor force attachment who have already established residence in the United States. By using immigrant-specific rates measured in the U.S. context rather than home-country demographic statistics, the calibration accounts for self-selection effects (EB migrants are positively selected on education and career orientation).

Spouse Presence Calibration Spouse accompaniment rates are estimated using ACS data on marital status. For each modeled nationality, the model calculates the weighted proportion of foreign-born workers aged 25–65 who are married with a spouse present in the household. This measure directly captures whether an immigrant worker has an accompanying spouse in the United States, which is the relevant parameter for derivative beneficiary eligibility.

Table 9: Spouse Presence Probability by Nationality

Nationality	Spouse Probability
India	0.794
China	0.673
South Korea	0.664
Brazil	0.657
Philippines	0.647
Other	0.582

Source: Author’s calculations using data from IPUMS USA (Ruggles et al., 2025).

Dependent Children Calibration The number of dependent children per worker is calibrated using ACS data on own children in the household. For each nationality, the model calculates both the weighted mean number of children and the weighted standard deviation, enabling realistic variance in family sizes.

Table 10: Dependent Children Distribution (Conditional on Spouse)

Nationality	Mean Children	Std Dev Children
South Korea	1.093	1.094
India	1.017	0.937
Other	1.014	1.193
Philippines	0.958	1.090
Brazil	0.894	1.020
China	0.854	0.947

Source: Author’s calculations using data from IPUMS USA (Ruggles et al., 2025).

Child Entry Age Calibration To calibrate entry age distributions for immigrant children, the model uses IPUMS ACS data on foreign-born children linked to foreign-born parents within households.

The entry age calculation is derived from ACS respondent data on foreign-born children (those with a country of birth outside the United States). For each foreign-born child, the model calculates the age at which that child entered the U.S. by comparing the child’s current age to the parent’s immigration year. Specifically, a child’s entry age is estimated as their current age minus the number of years that have elapsed since the parent immigrated. Children born in the United States are explicitly excluded from this analysis because they are not representative of the derivative beneficiary population accompanying parents through the EB visa queue.

Table 11: Child U.S. Entry Age Distribution

Nationality	Mean Entry Age	Std Dev Entry Age
Brazil	2.25	4.22
Other	1.19	3.08
Philippines	1.08	2.93
India	1.03	2.72
China	1.02	2.87
South Korea	0.80	2.71

Source: Author’s calculations using data from IPUMS USA (Ruggles et al., 2025).

Adjustment for Pre-Filing Residence Period The IPUMS-derived entry ages represent the age at which children entered the United States, not the age at which they entered the EB visa queue. Employment-based workers typically reside in the United States on temporary nonimmigrant status (H-1B, L-1, or similar) for several years before filing a petition to begin the permanent residence process.

To account for this pre-filing residence period, the simulation adds a fixed offset of 3 years to each child’s U.S. entry age to estimate their age when their parent entered the EB queue:

$$\text{Age at queue entry} = \text{Age at U.S. Entry} + 3 \text{ years} \quad (1)$$

After applying the 3-year adjustment, the effective mean child age at queue entry becomes approximately 4.0 years, with standard deviation of 2.79 years.

Joint Family Structure and Probabilistic Child Generation The simulation implements spouse presence and children count as a two-stage probabilistic process:

1. **Stage 1: Spouse Presence Determination.** For each worker entering the visa queue, the simulation executes a Bernoulli trial with success probability equal to the worker’s nationality-specific spouse probability. If the trial succeeds, the worker is assigned an accompanying spouse; if it fails, the worker has no spouse.
2. **Stage 2: Children Count Generation (Conditional on Spouse).** If and only if the worker has a spouse, the simulation generates the number of dependent children. Children count is sampled from a normal distribution with nationality-specific mean and standard deviation, rounded to the nearest non-negative integer. Workers without spouses receive zero dependent children.

Special Population Override: SIJS The Special Immigrant Juvenile Status (SIJS) pathway serves unaccompanied minors who have been abused, abandoned, or neglected, and for whom family reunification is not viable. SIJS

beneficiaries are minors petitioning for themselves and therefore have fundamentally different family structures than employment-based workers.

To reflect this unique population, the simulation overrides demographic parameters for SIJS: spouse probability is set to 0.0 and children count is set to 0.0, regardless of nationality. This ensures SIJS beneficiaries do not generate dependent children who could age out, which would be nonsensical given the pathway's purpose and beneficiary characteristics.

Child Lifecycle Processing and Annual Sequencing The simulation tracks each dependent child through a state-based lifecycle model with four mutually exclusive states.

- **Dependent:** Children enter the simulation in the dependent state when their parent joins the visa allocation queue. Dependent children remain in this state as long as two conditions hold: (1) the child is under age 21, (2) the parent remains in the visa queue awaiting allocation. The dependent state is the only non-terminal state; all children eventually transition out of it into one of the three terminal states.
- **Saved:** Children transition from dependent to saved when their parent successfully receives an employment-based visa and converts from temporary to permanent resident status. Upon the parent's conversion, all dependent children associated with that parent are immediately reclassified as saved, reflecting their successful derivation of permanent residence through the parent's petition.
- **Aged Out:** Children transition from dependent to aged out when they reach age 21 while their parent remains in the visa queue. Derivative beneficiary eligibility terminates when a child turns 21 (subject to CSPA adjustments).
- **Returned:** Children transition from dependent to returned when their parent departs the U.S. immigration system before receiving a visa. Parent departure can occur through emigration, death, or abandonment of the immigration process. When a parent exits the system, all associated dependent children are reclassified as returned, reflecting their removal from the visa queue.

Annual Processing Sequence and Causal Ordering Each simulation year executes child lifecycle operations in a fixed sequence designed to prevent double-counting and correctly resolve edge cases where multiple events could affect a child's status in the same year.

1. **Step 1: Child Creation.** At the beginning of each simulation year, new dependent children are generated for workers entering the EB visa queue. For each new worker with a spouse (determined by the probabilistic process described above), the simulation samples the number of children from nationality-specific distributions and assigns each child an initial age drawn from nationality-specific entry age distributions. The 3-year pre-filing residence adjustment is added to each child's entry age to account for the period between U.S. arrival and entry of an EB visa queue.
2. **Step 2: Queue Exit Processing.** Workers who exit the immigration system are identified and removed from the visa queue. For each exiting worker, all associated dependent children transition immediately from dependent to returned status. This step occurs before visa allocation to ensure that exiting workers do not receive visas and that their children are properly accounted for as returned rather than remaining in the dependent pool.
3. **Step 3: Visa Allocation.** The visa allocation engine processes workers in the queue according to statutory allocation rules. Workers who receive visas convert from temporary to permanent resident status.
4. **Step 4: Child Saving.** Immediately following visa allocation, all dependent children whose parents converted to permanent status are reclassified from dependent to saved. This step is executed before child aging to ensure that children whose parents receive visas in the current year are protected from aging out, even if the child would otherwise turn 21 in the same year. The save-first protocol implements an optimistic interpretation of CSPA provisions.
5. **Step 5: Child Aging.** Finally, all remaining dependent children (those whose parents did not receive visas and did not exit the queue) age by one year. Children whose age reaches 21 during this step transition from dependent to aged out.

Rationale for Save-First Sequencing The ordering of child saving before child aging is critical for correctly handling edge cases and reflects a deliberate modeling assumption about CSPA protections. Consider a child born in 2004. In simulation year 2025, the child turns 21 years old. Suppose the parent also receives their EB visa in 2025. Two outcomes are possible depending on sequencing:

- **Age-first approach:** The child ages to 21 before the parent's visa is processed, triggering an aged-out classification. Even though the parent receives a visa in the same year, the child has already lost eligibility.

- **Save-first approach:** The parent’s visa conversion is processed first, triggering immediate reclassification of all dependent children to saved status. When the aging step subsequently executes, this child is no longer in the dependent pool and therefore cannot age out.

The simulation implements the save-first protocol, classifying same-year cases as saved rather than aged out. This represents an optimistic assumption that CSPA provisions will protect children when visa allocation and the 21st birthday occur in close temporal proximity.

4.2.4 Non-Visa Queue Exit Rate Calibration

The simulation models queue exits through three primary mechanisms: visa allocation, child aging out, and non-visa queue departures. This section addresses the third mechanism.

Sources of Non-Visa Queue Exits Workers may exit the employment-based visa queue before receiving a visa through several pathways:

- **Emigration:** Voluntary departure from the United States, including return migration to the country of origin or migration to third countries.
- **Mortality:** Death of the principal applicant terminates the associated EB petition and removes both the worker and any derivative beneficiaries from the queue.
- **Petition Withdrawal and Abandonment:** Workers may abandon their initial green card pursuit when career transitions result in the individual no longer meeting the eligibility criteria for the original category. Additionally, the U.S. employment-based system permits the filing of multiple petitions, either concurrently or sequentially, across different preference categories (e.g., EB-2 and EB-3) or within the same category through multiple employers. When one petition is approved and the beneficiary secures permanent residence through that pathway, any remaining pending or previously approved petitions are typically withdrawn. Moreover, workers may also shift to family-based sponsorship (e.g., through marriage to a U.S. citizen), which would remove them from the EB visa queue.

Data Limitations and Calibration Approach USCIS does not publish longitudinal tracking data on non-visa queue exits; this data gap necessitates a calibration-based approach. We calibrate annual queue exit rates to ensure the synthetic backlog (as of Q3 2025) matches aggregate characteristics of USCIS administrative data on approved petitions awaiting visa availability.

Calibrated Exit Rate Structure The calibration approach employs a two-dimensional rate structure determined by both nationality and EB category.

EB-1 In the model, the EB-1 category exhibits the second lowest exit rate, with uniformity across nationalities. Beneficiaries in this category possess exceptional credentials. Accordingly, the opportunity cost of emigration from the U.S. is uniformly high regardless of nationality, as home-country labor markets rarely offer comparable positions for individuals at the pinnacle of their fields.

Nationality	Annual Exit Rate
All Countries	0.25%

EB-2 The model assigns substantially higher annual exit rates to Chinese EB-2 beneficiaries (17.25%) relative to Indian EB-2 beneficiaries (4.00%), with intermediate rates (5.50%) applied to Brazil, the Philippines, South Korea, and the residual “Other” category. These asymmetric exit rates reflect underlying structural and behavioral differences in return-migration incentives across national origin groups.

Chinese EB-2 beneficiaries exhibit the highest exit rates in the category because a distinct set of economic and institutional factors generates comparatively strong incentives to return. First, China’s technology, finance, and advanced manufacturing sectors have expanded at a pace unmatched by other major sending countries (Blaugher and Gordon, 2025). Highly skilled migrants from rapidly growing economies tend to return at higher rates, as rising domestic opportunities reduce the opportunity cost of repatriation (Baruch et al., 2007). China’s accelerated wage

growth for high-skilled cohorts thus meaningfully counterbalances the perceived benefits of remaining in the U.S. queue for extended periods.

Second, China has developed robust and institutionalized “talent return” infrastructures such as the Thousand Talents Plan that materially lower the frictions associated with re-entry into domestic labor markets (Jia, 2018). These programs provide structured pathways for returnees to re-integrate into research, industry, and entrepreneurial ecosystems, further elevating realized exit rates relative to other nationalities.

By contrast, Indian EB-2 beneficiaries receive substantially lower modeled exit rates (4.00%), reflecting structural labor-market conditions that dampen incentives for return. High-skilled Indian nationals exhibit emigration rates roughly twice the global average (Amazadeh et al., 2024). Although this measure captures outbound rather than return migration, it constitutes a strong revealed-preference indicator: highly skilled Indian nationals demonstrate persistently high propensities to remain abroad, suggesting considerable structural disincentives to repatriation.

Additionally, Indian EB-2 applicants are disproportionately concentrated in occupations such as software engineering, computer science, and systems architecture (Im et al., 2025). For these cohorts, the U.S. wage premium remains exceptionally high relative to identically skilled workers in India (Clemens et al., 2008), substantially weakening the economic rationale for abandoning the multiyear path to permanent residency.

Table 13: EB-2 Annual Exit Rates

Nationality	Annual Exit Rate
China	17.25%
Brazil	5.50%
Philippines	5.50%
South Korea	5.50%
Other	5.50%
India	4.00%

EB-3 The EB-3 exit-rate structure in the model reflects nationality-specific dynamics rooted in the occupational composition and mobility incentives characteristic of each group’s EB-3 population.

Filipino beneficiaries receive the highest EB-3 exit rate (22.0%), reflecting their pronounced concentration in nursing and related health-care professions, a sector where Filipinos constitute roughly one-third of the entire foreign-born workforce in the U.S. (Eugenio, 2024). Because global labor shortages in healthcare generate exceptionally high cross-border mobility, these workers possess robust alternative options. Specifically, European health systems offer strong and immediate demand for foreign-trained nurses (Lauren et al., 2025), creating attractive diversionary pathways that increase the likelihood of departure from the U.S. queue.

China’s EB-3 exit rate is set at 21.5%, broadly aligning with the high-churn dynamic of its EB-2 cohort. This reflects the return incentives driving Chinese migration patterns, including rapidly expanding domestic labor markets, rising wage competitiveness, and well-developed talent-recruitment programs. The specific parameter value was empirically calibrated to match USCIS administrative inventory; the fact that it slightly exceeds the EB-2 baseline suggests that additional factors may further amplify these structural return incentives. While the precise micro-foundations of this differential warrant future study, the calibrated rate effectively captures the aggregate attrition necessary to reproduce the observed backlog volume.

India’s EB-3 exit rate (4.0%) mirrors its EB-2 rate as a considerable share of Indian EB-3 applicants are “downgraded” EB-2 professionals (Malik and Ignachkov, 2022), meaning that the EB-3 queue for India is populated substantively by advanced-degree engineers and IT professionals whose wage gains, career trajectories, and technological complementarities are greatest in the United States. These factors generate strong retention incentives, leaving exit rates consistently low across both EB categories.

Brazil, South Korea, and the “Other” nationality category are assigned the lowest EB-3 exit rates (1.0%), lower than both their own EB-2 baselines and the Indian EB-3 rate (4.0%). This floor-level attrition reflects a critical distinction in queue composition: unlike the Indian EB-3 queue, which is saturated with “downgraded” advanced-degree professionals possessing higher global mobility, these category-nationality cohorts reflect the category’s statutory design, comprising a heterogeneous mix of skilled trades, technicians, and semi-professional workers. These groups generally possess fewer globally portable credentials and consequently face higher barriers to accessing alternative international labor markets (Global Education Monitoring Report Team, 2018, p. 57), suppressing exit rates.

Table 14: EB-3 Annual Exit Rates

Nationality	Annual Exit Rate
Philippines	22.0%
China	21.5%
India	4.0%
Brazil	1.0%
South Korea	1.0%
Other	1.0%

EB-4 EB-4 exhibits uniformly elevated exit rates across all nationalities (13.00%), as the structural characteristics of EB-4 pathways generate high attrition independent of nationality.

Religious Workers and Status-Limit Constraints Many EB-4 applicants enter the U.S. on R-1 status, which is subject to strict time limits and requires employers to file Form I-129 petitions for extensions. Although extensions may be granted for an additional 30 months, total R-1 stay cannot exceed five years. After that limit, individuals must depart the United States for at least one year unless they obtain another status or a green card (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.c). These constraints create substantial status-management burdens, contributing to higher exit rates.

SIJS Beneficiaries and Institutional Transition SIJS beneficiaries, who constitute a substantial portion of the “Other” nationality category, face unique vulnerabilities that elevate attrition risks. Many spend multiple years in the backlog and reach legal adulthood while awaiting processing. Although they do not formally “age out” of visa eligibility like derivative children, they often exit juvenile dependency systems, losing access to critical social support services (Dworsky et al., 2013).

This transition to independence frequently introduces severe instability, with one-third of youth leaving foster care experience homelessness or housing insecurity during the shift to adulthood (Dworsky et al., 2013). Such economic precarity can make it substantially harder for SIJS beneficiaries to sustain the resources needed to navigate a multi-year administrative process such as paying for legal assistance, accessing transportation to appointments, or managing repeated documentation requests. These burdens increase the likelihood of missed deadlines or incomplete filings. Consequently, SIJS youth plausibly face higher rates of attrition, raising their overall exit rates.

Table 15: EB-4 Annual Exit Rates

Nationality	Annual Exit Rate
All Countries	13.00%

EB-5 EB-5 applicants are assigned the lowest and uniform exit rate (0.10%) across all nationalities. Immigrant investors commit substantial capital to job-creating enterprises, with the standard minimum investment currently set at \$1.8 million (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.d). These financial commitments create a strong lock-in effect, as abandoning the permanent residence process would result in significant financial loss.

Table 16: EB-5 Annual Exit Rates

Nationality	Annual Exit Rate
All Countries	0.10%

Calibration Process Decisions to remain in or exit the queue are influenced by multiple factors, including economic mobility prospects, home-country labor-market conditions, ability to maintain lawful presence, tolerance for long waits, and migration costs. Given this complexity, exit rates cannot be determined solely from theory and require careful parameter tuning.

The model’s nationality- and category-specific exit parameters were calibrated through an iterative procedure in which exit rates were adjusted incrementally, and simulation outputs were evaluated against observed USCIS data (June 2025) at each step. The procedure aimed to minimize deviations simultaneously across all relevant dimensions.

Calibration targeted three empirical benchmarks to ensure fidelity to real-world system behavior:

1. **Aggregate backlog magnitude:** Total principal applicants across all EB categories and nationalities.
2. **Category-specific distribution:** Relative shares across EB categories, particularly EB-2 and EB-3, as they contain the largest population of children at the risk of aging out.
3. **Nationality-category interactions:** Backlog levels for major nationality groups (India and China).

Calibration Procedure The calibration procedure began by initializing exit parameters uniformly across all nationalities and EB categories. The model was then executed to generate synthetic backlog outcomes under this initial parameter set, and simulated outputs were compared against USCIS June 2025 data using absolute backlog deviations, category-specific deviations, and nationality–category deviations. Exit rates were incrementally adjusted for specific nationalities and categories based on the observed discrepancies, and the simulation was rerun to assess the resulting fit. This process was repeated iteratively until changes in fit fell below a predefined tolerance threshold, ensuring that the calibrated parameters produced a stable and consistent representation of real-world backlog dynamics.

4.2.5 Statutory Visa Allocation Parameters

Annual Visa Supply The employment-based visa system operates under a statutory cap of 140,000 visas per year. In addition to this base allocation, employment-based categories receive additional visas from family-based preference category spillover when family preference categories are undersubscribed.

Two-Phase Visa Supply Architecture Visa supply is calibrated using historical actual allocations for FY2013–FY2024 and a constant baseline allocation for FY2024 onward.

Phase 1: Historical EB Visa Pool (FY2013–FY2024) For the synthetic backlog reconstruction period, the model uses employment-based visa allocation totals from Department of State data. These historical totals reflect the combined statutory base allocation (140,000 visas) plus actual family-based spillover in each fiscal year:

Table 17: Historical Employment-Based Visa Totals (FY2013–FY2024)

Fiscal Year	Total EB Visas
2013	161,269
2014	151,359
2015	143,952
2016	140,350
2017	139,604
2018	139,483
2019	140,586
2020	147,153
2021	195,507
2022	275,250
2023	193,928
2024	167,394

Source: U.S. Department of State, Report of the Visa Office (Annual Reports) (U.S. Department of State, n.d.b).

The COVID-Era Visa Supply Shock (FY2021–FY2023) The employment-based immigration system experienced a significant, exogenous supply shock during fiscal years 2021–2023, representing the largest deviation from statutory baselines in modern history. Pandemic-related disruptions to consular processing resulted in a massive underutilization of family-sponsored visas, which were reallocated to the employment-based cap in subsequent years. This spillover generated a temporary but substantial surge in employment-based visa availability.

Phase 2: Forward Projection Baseline (FY2024 Onward) Beginning in FY2024, the simulation transitions to a constant annual visa pool of 167,394 visas. This baseline comprises the statutory base allocation (140,000 visas) and the FY2024 family-based spillover (27,394 visas).

EB Category Statutory Shares and Base Allocations The 167,394 annual employment-based visas are distributed across five employment-based preference categories (EB-1 through EB-5) according to statutory percentages.

Table 18: EB Category Statutory Allocations (Baseline 167,394 Visas)

EB Category	Statutory Share	Base Allocation
EB-1	28.6%	47,874
EB-2	28.6%	47,874
EB-3	28.6%	47,874
EB-4	7.1%	11,886
EB-5	7.1%	11,886
Total	100%	167,394

These allocations represent base allocations before cascade spillover (detailed in Section 4.2.6).

Per-Country Limitation: The 7% Cap The Immigration Act of 1990 specifies that no single country shall receive more than 7% of the total employment-based visa pool within each EB category in a given fiscal year (Ennis, 2024). This per-country cap applies to total visa consumption (principal applicant plus derivative spouses and dependent children), not merely to the count of principal applicants (Kandel et al., 2022).

For a given EB category with allocation X visas, the per-country cap is calculated as:

$$\text{Per-Country Cap (category)} = 0.07 \times X \quad (2)$$

For example, in fiscal year 2024 with EB-2 base allocation of 47,874 visas, the per-country cap is:

$$\text{Per-Country Cap (EB-2)} = 0.07 \times 47,874 = 3,351 \text{ visas per country}$$

This means no single country can consume more than 3,351 EB-2 visas (across all principals and their families combined) in a given fiscal year. However, there are exceptions to this rule that come into play if the number of visas available for an EB category exceeds the number of qualified applicants for that category (with the 7% cap applied), which will be delineated in Section 4.3.2.

Table 19: Per-Country Caps by EB Category (Baseline)

EB Category	Base Allocation	Per-Country Cap (7%)
EB-1	47,874	3,351
EB-2	47,874	3,351
EB-3	47,874	3,351
EB-4	11,885	832
EB-5	11,887	832

Visa Consumption and Family-Adjusted Allocation A critical aspect of per-country cap implementation is that caps apply to total visa consumption, not principal count (Kandel et al., 2022). An applicant with a spouse and two dependent children consumes 4 visas toward a nation’s per-country cap, not 1 visa. This family-adjusted consumption means that countries with greater average family sizes face tighter de facto per-country constraints than countries with smaller average family sizes.

The visa cost is constructed annually through the following procedure:

1. **Step 1:** The model iterates through all dependent children currently in the dependent children cohort. For each child, the simulation identifies the parent worker’s ID and increments a counter for that parent. This aggregation creates a lookup table mapping worker IDs to current dependent child counts.
2. **Step 2:** For each temporary worker, the model calculates:

$$\text{Visa Cost} = 1 \text{ (principal)} + \text{spouse_count} + \text{children_count} \quad (3)$$

3. **Step 3:** The calculated visa cost is stored in a dictionary indexed by worker ID. This cache is built once per year at the start of each visa allocation cycle (immediately before visa processing begins) and remains immutable during that cycle’s processing. After the allocation cycle completes and children are saved or aged out, the cache becomes stale and is discarded.

Why Annual Rebuild is Critical The visa cost cache must be rebuilt every year because dependent children counts change. If the cache were not rebuilt, it would contain stale information: it might, for example, show a worker as having 2 dependent children when that worker now has 0 (because children aged out).

4.2.6 Cascade Flow Structure

The simulation mirrors how the employment-based visa allocation system implements a cascade mechanism to prevent visa waste when petition demand is insufficient to exhaust an EB category's allocation.

The cascade operates as follows, in accordance to Kandel et al. (2022):

- **EB-4 and EB-5 cascade to EB-1:** Any EB-4 and EB-5 visas flow to EB-1 allocation.
- **EB-1 cascades to EB-2:** Any EB-1 visas (including cascaded EB-4/5 visas) not used flow to EB-2 allocation.
- **EB-2 cascades to EB-3:** Any EB-2 visas (including cascaded EB-1 visas) not used flow to EB-3 allocation.
- **EB-3 unused visas are lost:** Any EB-3 visas not used (including cascaded EB-2 visas) are forfeited.

Table 20: Statutory Cascade Flow

Source Category	Unused Visas Flow To
EB-4	EB-1
EB-5	EB-1
EB-1	EB-2
EB-2	EB-3
EB-3	Lost

4.3 Visa Allocation Procedures and Scenario Implementation

4.3.1 Uncapped Scenario Visa Allocation

The uncapped scenario models a policy counterfactual in which employment-based visas are allocated strictly by priority date within each EB category.

Step 1: Dynamic Visa Supply Calculation The simulation first determines the visa budget for each EB category sequentially according to the statutory cascade order (EB-4 and EB-5 → EB-1 → EB-2 → EB-3). Each category begins with its statutory baseline (e.g., 28.6% of the annual limit), and any unused visas from preceding categories in the cascade are added as spillovers.

Step 2: Global Queue Construction All active applicants within a given EB category are aggregated into a single global queue, sorted strictly by priority date.

Step 3: Sequential Allocation Applicants are processed sequentially in priority-date order. The algorithm evaluates a single constraint for each applicant:

- **Category-level constraint:** Does the EB category have sufficient remaining visas to cover the applicant and their accompanying family members?

Step 4: Conversion or Deferral If the constraint is satisfied, the applicant and all derivative family members are granted permanent resident status, and the total visa cost is deducted from the category's annual allocation. If the constraint is violated, allocation for that category halts immediately, and the current applicant, along with all subsequent applicants, is deferred to the following fiscal year.

4.3.2 Capped Scenario: Two-Pass Per-Country Allocation

The capped scenario incorporates the 7% per-country limitation on visa allocations within each EB category.

A critical statutory exception to the strict per-country cap applies when visa waste would otherwise occur. If a category's visa allocation cannot be fully utilized due to per-country caps (i.e., all qualified applicants from countries below the cap are exhausted, but oversubscribed countries still have applicants waiting), then the per-country cap is effectively

suspended for remaining applicants, allowing unused visas to be allocated without country-of-birth restrictions (U.S. Department of State, n.d.c). Accordingly, the simulation model utilizes a two-pass approach to ensure that this processing procedure is accurately represented.

Step 1: Visa Supply Determination As in the uncapped scenario, the total visa budget for each EB category is calculated, including any spillovers from higher-priority categories.

Step 2: Pass 1 Allocation (Constrained) Applicants are processed in priority-date order within each EB category. Two constraints are evaluated for each applicant:

- **Category-level constraint:** Are sufficient visas available within the category?
- **Country-level constraint:** Would allocating this visa cause the applicant’s country to exceed its 7% cap?

Outcome:

If both constraints are satisfied, the applicant and their dependents are granted permanent status. If the country-level constraint is violated, the applicant is deferred to Pass 2. If the category-level constraint is violated, allocation for the year ends, and remaining applicants are deferred to the following fiscal year.

Step 3: Pass 2 Allocation (Unconstrained) After Pass 1, deferred applicants from oversubscribed countries are processed again without per-country limitations. Remaining category visas are allocated strictly by priority date until the category’s allocation is fully used. Applicants exceeding available visas remain in the queue for the next fiscal year.

Illustrative Example Consider an EB-2 allocation of 47,874 visas with a 7% per-country cap of 3,351 visas.

- **Pass 1:** Applicants are processed sequentially within each country. Chinese applicants, for instance, are allocated visas up to the 3,351 cap. Additional Chinese applicants are deferred even though visas remain in the overall EB-2 category. Applicants from other countries are processed similarly up to their respective caps or until the category allocation is exhausted.
- **Pass 2:** Deferred applicants from oversubscribed countries are processed again without country-specific restrictions. Remaining category visas are allocated by priority date until the category allocation is fully used. Any applicants with a visa cost exceeding the available visas remain in the queue for the following year.

4.3.3 Within-Cohort Randomization to Mitigate Priority Date Granularity Limitations

Because priority dates in the simulation are specified only at annual granularity, multiple applicants from different nationalities may share the same priority date within a given year. Generating priority dates at a finer level, such as month or day, would require additional data and modeling complexity.

To address this, the model implements within-cohort randomization, whereby all applicants sharing the same entry year are randomly shuffled prior to allocation. This procedure applies consistently across both uncapped and capped allocation scenarios and effectively approximates the effects of day-level priority dates without requiring additional data or assumptions. For example, if ten EB-2 applicants obtain I-140 approvals in 2026—five from India and five from China—the randomization interweaves them rather than processing all applicants from a single nationality sequentially. This preserves first-in, first-out fairness within annual priority-date cohorts while providing an efficient substitute for finer-grained petition data.

4.4 Validation Assessment

4.4.1 Model Validation

Validation Data Sources The primary validation benchmark is the USCIS report “Number of Form I-140, I-360, I-526/E Approved Employment-Based Petitions Awaiting Visa Availability” from June 2025, the most recent publicly available release at the time of analysis (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b). The simulation produces a synthetic backlog as of 2025, enabling direct temporal comparison between simulated and observed queue states.

USCIS administrative reports disaggregate backlog data by five nationality groupings: China, India, Mexico, Philippines, and “Rest of World.” The simulation, by contrast, tracks six nationality categories based on top countries by I-140 receipt volume: India, China, Philippines, Brazil, South Korea, and “Other” (all remaining countries aggregated).

Because USCIS does not separately report Brazil or South Korea, two countries the simulation tracks explicitly, validation of these nationalities requires aggregation. For validation purposes, the simulation’s combined “Other

+ Brazil + South Korea” is compared to USCIS’s combined “Mexico + Rest of World,” representing the residual population after removing India, China, and the Philippines from both data sources. This aggregation approach enables meaningful comparison despite the differing nationality classification schemes.

Aggregate Backlog Validation The simulation produces a total backlog of 930,547 principal applicants across all employment-based categories, compared to 945,768 principal applicants reported by USCIS. The simulation underestimates the USCIS benchmark by 15,221 applicants, a difference of -1.6%.

Table 21: Aggregate Principal Backlog Comparison (June 2025)

Metric	USCIS (June 2025)	Simulation	Difference
Total Principal Applicants	945,768	930,547	-15,221 (-1.6%)

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Category-Level Backlog Count Validation Category-level count validation assesses whether the simulation correctly reproduces the count of backlogged applicants across the five employment-based preference categories (EB-1 through EB-5).

Table 22: Category-Level Backlog Count Validation

EB Category	USCIS (June 2025)	Simulation (Capped)	Difference	% Difference
EB-1	32,765	32,016	-749	-2.3%
EB-2	390,950	393,087	+2,137	+0.5%
EB-3	184,602	169,154	-15,448	-8.4%
EB-4	306,383	301,736	-4,647	-1.5%
EB-5	31,068	34,554	+3,486	+11.2%
Total	945,768	930,547	-15,221	-1.6%

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Category-Level Backlog Distribution Validation Category-level backlog distribution validation assesses whether the simulation correctly reproduces the distribution of backlogged applicants across the five employment-based preference categories (EB-1 through EB-5). All category distribution shares fall within ± 1.3 percentage points of USCIS benchmarks, indicating that the simulation correctly reproduces the structural composition of the employment-based backlog.

Table 23: Backlog Share Distribution Comparison

EB Category	USCIS Share	Simulation Share	Deviation
EB-1	3.5%	3.4%	-0.1%
EB-2	41.3%	42.2%	+0.9%
EB-3	19.5%	18.2%	-1.3%
EB-4	32.4%	32.4%	+0.0%
EB-5	3.3%	3.7%	+0.4%

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

India Validation: The Primary Age-Out Population India represents the largest single-nationality component of the employment-based backlog and faces the longest wait times due to per-country cap constraints.

The India EB-2 and EB-3 categories, where the vast majority of age-out risk is concentrated due to multi-decade wait times, are calibrated to within 1% of USCIS administrative data.

EB-5 backward projection is inaccurate because India’s proportion was likely a lot smaller in prior years than in FY2024, something that uniformly applying FY2024 distributions misses. However, this deviation is analytically

inconsequential for three reasons. First, EB-5 contributes negligibly to child age-outs, as the results will later show. Second, the absolute difference, 3,574 individuals, is trivial relative to an employment-based backlog numbering in the millions and therefore has no meaningful effect on any downstream conclusions. Third, the primary driver of the EB-5 backlog, China, exhibits only a 0.3% deviation in the model, demonstrating that the core component of EB-5 demand is captured with high accuracy.

Table 24: India Backlog Validation

EB Category	USCIS India	Simulation India	Difference	% Difference
EB-1	19,596	19,059	-537	-2.7%
EB-2	336,458	335,181	-1,277	-0.4%
EB-3	102,937	102,127	-810	-0.8%
EB-4	8,948	7,875	-1,073	-12.0%
EB-5	755	4,329	+3,574	+473.4%
TOTAL	468,694	468,571	-123	-0.0%

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

China Validation China represents the second-largest backlog by nationality and faces significant per-country cap constraints in EB-2 and EB-5 categories.

The simulation achieves strong accuracy for China’s aggregate employment-based backlog (-2.7%) and deviation from USCIS administrative data remains at approximately 5% or below across all significant categories (EB-1, EB-2, EB-3, and EB-5). These categories collectively account for nearly all Chinese employment-based principal applicants and drive the distributional consequences of both per-country caps and alternative allocation regimes.

The large percentage deviation in China EB-4 (-100%) doesn’t meaningfully alter results. In absolute terms, the EB-4 difference (1,527 individuals) is negligible and has no substantive bearing on age-out projections.

Table 25: China Backlog Validation

EB Category	USCIS China	Simulation China	Difference	% Difference
EB-1	13,169	12,957	-212	-1.6%
EB-2	34,608	35,604	+996	+2.9%
EB-3	12,536	12,136	-400	-3.2%
EB-4	1,527	0	-1,527	-100.0%
EB-5	30,313	30,225	-88	-0.3%
TOTAL	92,153	90,922	-1,231	-1.3%

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Philippines Validation The Philippines represents a significant presence in EB-3 skilled worker categories.

The simulation accurately captures the Philippines’ presence in EB-3 (+4.5% deviation), which is the category most relevant for Filipino beneficiaries. The deviations observed in EB-2 and EB-4, while large in percentage terms, correspond to small absolute differences (865 and 2,182 applicants, respectively). Given their limited numerical weight and the fact that Filipino backlogs are heavily concentrated in EB-3, these discrepancies have no substantive effect on the study’s conclusions.

Table 26: Philippines Backlog Validation

EB Category	USCIS Philippines	Simulation Philippines	Difference	% Difference
EB-1	0	0	+0	N/A
EB-2	138	0	-138	-100.0%
EB-3	20,948	21,813	+865	+4.1%
EB-4	2,668	486	-2,182	-81.8%
EB-5	0	0	+0	N/A
TOTAL	23,754	22,299	-1,455	-6.1%

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

"Other" Nationalities Validation As noted previously, the study aggregates Mexico and the Rest of the World in the USCIS administrative data. For the simulation, the corresponding aggregation combines the "Other," Brazil, and South Korea categories.

At the aggregate level, the simulation's "Other" population is accurate to within -3.3%, indicating that the model reliably captures the residual backlog after accounting for the three major origin countries (India, China, and the Philippines).

The EB-4 "Other" category exhibits excellent concordance with USCIS data (+0.5% deviation). This accuracy is especially important because EB-4 is dominated by the "Other" group.

The -31.3% deviation in the EB-3 "Other" category warrants further explanation. A substantial portion of USCIS's "Rest of World" classification for EB-3 consists of Mexican applicants. Because Mexico is not modeled explicitly, due to the absence of consistent, nationality-specific longitudinal data on I-140 filings, its omission necessarily introduces greater variation in this category than in others where major nationalities are directly parameterized. The resulting discrepancy reflects this structural data limitation rather than a systematic modeling error.

Although this represents the largest category-specific deviation in the simulation, it has minimal impact on long-run age-out projections for two reasons. First, the "Other" category accounts for only a small share of child age-outs, as shown in the results. Second, in absolute terms, the deviation of roughly 15,000 is small relative to the nearly one-million-person employment-based backlog projected for FY2025.

Table 27: Other Nationalities Backlog Validation

EB Category	USCIS (Mexico + ROW)	Simulation (Combined)	Difference	% Difference
EB-1	0	0	0	N/A
EB-2	19,746	22,302	+2,556	+12.9%
EB-3	48,181	33,078	-15,103	-31.3%
EB-4	293,240	293,861	+621	+0.2%
EB-5	0	0	0	N/A
TOTAL	361,167	349,241	-11,926	-3.3%

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

Critical Categories for Age-Out Analysis The following eight priority category-nationality combinations are collectively calibrated to within -0.3% of USCIS administrative data. These combinations represent 61.2% of the simulation's total employment-based backlog and account for essentially all children at risk of aging out, given that immigrants of these nationalities face the greatest constraints from the 7% per country cap, as evident by their backlog populations.

Table 28: Critical Categories Validation

Category	USCIS	Simulation	Difference	% Difference
India EB-1	19,596	19,059	-537	-2.7%
India EB-2	336,458	335,181	-1,277	-0.4%
India EB-3	102,937	102,127	-810	-0.8%
China EB-1	13,169	12,957	-212	-1.6%
China EB-2	34,608	35,604	+996	+2.9%
China EB-3	12,536	12,136	-400	-3.2%
China EB-5	30,313	30,225	-88	-0.3%
Philippines EB-3	20,948	21,813	+865	+4.1%
TOTAL	570,565	569,102	-1,463	-0.3%

Source: U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, Immigration and Citizenship Data portal (U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services, n.d.b).

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Per-Category and Aggregate Visa Consumption

Both policy scenarios process nearly identical total visa volumes over the 22-year simulation period (FY2013–FY2035). The uncapped scenario allocates 3,792,302 employment-based visas (including principal applicants, spouses, and dependent children), while the capped scenario allocates 3,792,100—a difference of only 202 visas (0.005%). This small discrepancy arises from edge-case situations in which the next applicant in line requires more visas (for the principal and dependents) than the number remaining in that category for the fiscal year. Because the simulation does not partially allocate visas to an applicant, the remaining visas in that category go unused. Crucially, the specific applicants who trigger these edge cases differ between the capped and uncapped scenarios due to the reordering of queues under per-country limits. As a result, the number of visas stranded varies slightly across scenarios. The negligible size of this divergence confirms that the model does not reduce aggregate visa utilization but redistributes visas across nationalities.

Equilibrium Stabilization of Category-Level Allocations The simulation reveals that category-level visa allocations converge to stable equilibrium values beginning in FY2024 and persisting through the projection endpoint (FY2035).

Table 29: Equilibrium Allocation Structure (FY2024–FY2035)

EB Category	Annual Allocation	Share of Total
EB-1	47,875	28.6%
EB-2	47,875	28.6%
EB-3	47,875	28.6%
EB-4	11,885	7.1%
EB-5	11,885	7.1%
Total	167,395	100.0%

Scenario Equivalence at the Category Level The equilibrium allocation structure is functionally identical across scenarios. Because category-level allocations are identical across scenarios and constant over time in the projection period, any differential outcomes between scenarios are attributable exclusively to nationality redistribution effects rather than aggregate or EB supply differences.

Table 30: Scenario Allocation Equivalence

Year	Uncapped Total	Capped Total	Difference
FY2024	167,393	167,395	+2
FY2030	167,394	167,395	+1
FY2035	167,394	167,395	+1

(a) Uncapped scenario

(b) Capped scenario (7% per-country cap)

Figure 1: EB category conversions over time across uncapped and capped scenarios, FY2013–FY2035.

5.1.1 Visa Consumption by Nationality

The redistribution of visa allocations across nationalities represents the most pronounced effect of per-country caps.

In the most notable case, Indian nationals experience a dramatic visa reduction of 951,282 allocations under per-country caps. Under the uncapped scenario, India receives 1,578,198 visas (41.6% of total), compared to only 626,916 (16.5%) under caps.

Interestingly, Chinese nationals experience only a marginal reduction (-8,846 visas, -1.8%). This shows that China’s comparatively higher non-visa queue exit rates and more diversified backlog distribution across EB categories limit queue accumulation, thereby moderating per-country cap constraint effects compared to India.

The “Other” nationality category experiences the largest absolute gain, receiving 756,915 additional visas (53.8% increase), reflecting visa capacity freed by constraining high-demand countries.

Table 31: Visa Consumption Differential by Nationality (FY2013–FY2035)

Nationality	Uncapped Visas	Uncapped Share	Capped Visas	Capped Share	Differential
India	1,578,198	41.6%	626,916	16.5%	-951,282
Other	1,405,971	37.1%	2,162,886	57.0%	+756,915
China	481,719	12.7%	472,873	12.5%	-8,846
South Korea	147,371	3.9%	209,168	5.5%	+61,797
Brazil	98,100	2.6%	200,120	5.3%	+102,020
Philippines	80,943	2.1%	120,137	3.2%	+39,194

5.1.2 Per-Nationality Visa Consumption Trajectories Over Time

The temporal evolution of visa consumption reveals how per-country cap constraints intensify as backlogs accumulate.

Early Period: Weak Constraint Binding During the early simulation years, visa consumption patterns remain relatively similar across scenarios because the simulation starts with minimal historical backlog. Focusing on the most salient case, Indian nationals, illustrates this effect most vividly: in FY2013, they received 55,185 visas under the uncapped scenario versus 46,297 under the capped scenario, a ratio of 1.2:1. This modest differential shows that per-country cap constraints bind only weakly when backlog depth is limited. With relatively shallow queues, beneficiaries from high-demand nations can still largely be accommodated in the capped scenario, aided by large Pass 2 spillovers.

Transition Period: Accelerating Constraint Intensification and Pass 2 Contraction By FY2017, the visa allocation ratio for Indian nationals widens substantially to 2.9:1 (54,847 uncapped vs. 18,749 capped), a 142% increase from the FY2013 ratio. As backlogs grow each fiscal year under the capped scenario, Pass 1 allocation mechanisms consume an increasing proportion of available visas, leaving fewer visas available for Pass 2 unconstrained reallocation.

In fact, EB-2 Pass 2 allocations in the simulation declined from 36,066 in FY2013 to 16,851 in FY2035, representing a significant reduction in Pass 2 visa availability as backlogs deepen. As Pass 2 allocations shrink in absolute terms, the mechanism by which per-country caps limit specific nationalities’ access becomes increasingly consequential for high-demand nationalities, whose share of visas per year becomes more strictly bounded at 7% per-category as Pass 2 opportunities diminish.

Figure 2: Annual Pass 2 visa allocations by EB category, FY2013–FY2035.

COVID-Era Surge: Divergent Outcomes by EB Category The COVID-era visa surge (FY2021–FY2023) produces category-specific effects that reveal interesting mechanics of the per-country cap and Pass 2 reallocation processes. In FY2022 (the surge peak), total employment-based visa allocations reached approximately 275,250. This surge affected categories differentially based on each category’s Pass 2 allocation capacity:

- **EB-1 (Priority Workers):** EB-1 developed a limited backlog by FY2022 given the simulation’s initiation in FY2013. Consequently, Pass 1 demand from other countries’ backlogs was modest, leaving substantial visa capacity for Pass 2 allocation. During the surge, Pass 2 visas were allocated via FIFO priority date without per-country restrictions. Indian EB-1 beneficiaries, with accumulated earlier priority dates from years of cap-constrained processing, received disproportionate allocation from the expanded Pass 2 pool, resulting in a high capped-scenario allocation (41,847) in the simulation. A similar line of logic applies to Chinese EB-1 applicants, though smaller in magnitude.
- **EB-2, EB-3, EB-4:** In contrast to EB-1, there was a considerable backlog here from the “Other” category. Accordingly, not as many visas went to Pass 2 allocation in the simulation, meaning that countries with the largest backlogs in those categories didn’t benefit to the extent of EB-1 from the COVID-era surge in family-based spillovers.

Figure 3: Visa consumption by nationality, all EB categories (uncapped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 4: Visa consumption by nationality, all EB categories (capped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 5: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-1 category (uncapped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 6: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-1 category (capped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 7: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-2 category (uncapped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 8: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-2 category (capped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 9: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-3 category (uncapped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 10: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-3 category (capped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 11: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-4 category (uncapped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 12: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-4 category (capped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 13: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-5 category (uncapped), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 14: Visa consumption by nationality, EB-5 category (capped), FY2013–FY2035.

5.2 Backlog Accumulation Dynamics

5.2.1 Total Queue Backlog Trajectory

Counterintuitively, the capped scenario produces a smaller principal applicant backlog by FY2035 (1,539,419) than the uncapped scenario (1,576,199), despite per-country caps constraining visa allocations to high-demand nationalities. This paradox illuminates how per-country caps generate human costs through mechanisms not captured by aggregate backlog metrics.

The Queue Dynamics Equation Backlog size at any point in time reflects the balance of inflows and outflows:

$$\text{Backlog}_{t+1} = \text{Backlog}_t + \text{Inflows}_t - \text{Outflows}_t \quad (4)$$

Where outflows comprise three components:

$$\text{Outflows}_t = \text{Visa Allocations}_t + \text{Queue-Exits}_t + \text{Age-Outs}_t \quad (5)$$

The counterintuitive backlog pattern emerges because per-country caps alter the nationality composition of queue exits through category-specific mechanisms. The uncapped scenario produces higher total queue exits than the capped scenario (140,633 vs. 118,756 annually in FY2035, differential of 21,877), driven by differential queue exit rates across nationalities in EB-2 and EB-3 categories.

EB-2 Exit Rate Spike EB-2 exhibits the most pronounced principal queue exit differential between scenarios, driven by how per-country caps redistribute queue composition across nationalities with heterogeneous exit rates.

India and the “Other” nationality category dominate EB-2 demand, constituting 81.5% and 8.7% of the capped EB-2 backlog, respectively. These groups also display distinct annual exit rates: 4.00% for India and 5.50% for “Other.”

Under uncapped allocation, Indian applicants (who have comparatively low exit rates) would experience shorter waits, while applicants from “Other” nationalities (who have comparatively higher exit rates) would face longer waits. This compositional shift increases total exits, as applicants more likely to exit during the wait (the “Other” group) face longer waits, while those less likely to exit (Indian applicants) move through more quickly.

China’s EB-2 exit rate (17.25%) is far higher than those of both India and “Other,” but China’s comparatively smaller backlog share (12.5% capped vs. 8.3% uncapped), relative to India and “Other” combined, limits its influence on overall exit patterns. Consequently, the dominant drivers of the EB-2 exit differential are the effects of India and “Other” nationalities.

Across other EB categories, exit-rate differences between the capped and uncapped scenarios also arise from the redistribution of wait times across nationalities with varying exit propensities. In fact, EB-3, EB-4, and EB-5 all exhibit higher exit rates under the capped scenario. However, these effects are minor relative to EB-2, where the reweighting of nationalities has the strongest impact and where principal-applicant exit rates are higher in the uncapped scenario.

Figure 15: Difference in queue exits between the capped and uncapped scenarios, FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 16: Total queue exits by EB category (uncapped scenario, no per-country cap), FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 17: Total queue exits by EB category (capped scenario, 7% per-country cap), FY2013–FY2035.

At the same time, however, the capped scenario generates far larger child age-out outflows (59,043 additional age-outs) over the projection period relative to uncapped (these dynamics are examined in detail in subsequent sections).

Crucially, the overall impact on the total backlog reflects the interaction of these offsetting forces. The reduction in principal-applicant emigration under caps (21,877 fewer exits annually by FY2035) is outweighed by the increase in child age-outs (59,043 additional exits over the period), resulting in higher total outflows and therefore a smaller long-run backlog under the capped scenario.

Crucially, this smaller principal-applicant backlog under caps should not be interpreted as more efficient visa allocation. Rather, it reflects that per-country caps force a greater share of applicants, particularly children, out of the system altogether.

Figure 18: Total backlog accumulation in uncapped and capped scenarios, FY2013–FY2035.

5.2.2 Category-Specific Backlog Distribution

The distribution of the backlog across EB categories as well as the sizes of backlogs across different EB categories are similar across both the capped and uncapped scenarios in the simulation end date, FY2035.

Table 32: Category-Specific Backlog Distribution (FY2035)

Category	Principal Applicants (Uncapped)	Principal Applicants (Capped)	Percent Difference
EB-1	138,434	132,214	-4.5%
EB-2	613,020	609,648	-0.6%
EB-3	326,301	296,150	-9.2%
EB-4	463,985	467,226	+0.7%
EB-5	34,459	34,181	-0.8%
Total	1,576,199	1,539,419	-2.3%

Figure 19: Final EB category backlogs after FY2013–FY2035 simulation period. Bars show both principals-only (solid color) and total backlog including dependents (hatched pattern).

However, there are discrepancies in the nationality-level composition of those categories. The EB-1 backlog exhibits the most striking nationality-level divergence between scenarios. Under capped allocation, India and China comprise 99.9% of backlog (78,327 and 53,867 applicants respectively), while all other nationalities have zero or negligible representation. Under uncapped allocation, this concentration inverts dramatically: “Other” nationalities comprise 38.7% of backlog (53,518 applicants), India declines to 32.0%, and China to 21.8%, while Brazil, South Korea, and Philippines together comprise 7.5%.

Table 33: EB-1 Backlog by Nationality

Nationality	Uncapped	Uncapped %	Capped	Capped %	Differential
India	44,313	32.0%	78,327	59.2%	+34,014 (+76.8%)
China	30,174	21.8%	53,867	40.7%	+23,693 (+78.5%)
Other	53,518	38.7%	0	0.0%	-53,518 (-100.0%)
Philippines	706	0.5%	0	0.0%	-706 (-100.0%)
South Korea	3,366	2.4%	0	0.0%	-3,366 (-100.0%)
Brazil	6,357	4.6%	20	0.0%	-6,337 (-99.7%)
Total	138,434	100.0%	132,214	100.0%	-6,220 (-4.5%)

Figure 20: Final EB-1 category backlogs after FY2013–FY2035 simulation period. Bars show both principals-only (solid color) and total backlog including dependents (hatched pattern).

The EB-2 backlog exhibits the most extreme concentration of backlog on a single nationality under per-country caps. India comprises 81.5% of capped EB-2 backlog (496,933 applicants) compared to 56.0% under uncapped allocation (343,411 applicants), a differential of 153,522 additional Indian applicants. “Other” nationality share increases from 8.7% under caps to 29.2% under uncapped allocation, representing 126,325 fewer applicants under caps. China maintains relatively stable representation (7.5% capped vs. 8.3% uncapped).

Table 34: EB-2 Backlog by Nationality

Nationality	Uncapped	Uncapped %	Capped	Capped %	Differential
India	343,411	56.0%	496,933	81.5%	+153,522 (+44.7%)
China	50,997	8.3%	45,988	7.5%	-5,009 (-9.8%)
Other	179,190	29.2%	52,865	8.7%	-126,325 (-70.5%)
Philippines	1,869	0.3%	0	0.0%	-1,869 (-100.0%)
South Korea	13,720	2.2%	3,426	0.6%	-10,294 (-75.0%)
Brazil	23,833	3.9%	10,436	1.7%	-13,397 (-56.2%)
Total	613,020	100.0%	609,648	100.0%	-3,372 (-0.6%)

Figure 21: Final EB-2 category backlogs after FY2013–FY2035 simulation period. Bars show both principals-only (solid color) and total backlog including dependents (hatched pattern).

The EB-3 backlog demonstrates more balanced nationality distribution than EB-2, though India remains the dominant nationality under caps. India comprises 47.5% of capped EB-3 backlog (140,607 applicants) compared to 21.8% under uncapped allocation (71,083 applicants), a differential of 69,524 additional Indian applicants. The Philippines maintains a substantial presence in both scenarios (10.0% capped, 9.8% uncapped), with 29,709 and 32,081 applicants respectively. “Other” nationality share increases from 31.2% under caps to 52.9% under uncapped allocation, while China, South Korea, and Brazil together comprise 11.3% under caps and 15.5% under uncapped allocation.

Table 35: EB-3 Backlog by Nationality

Nationality	Uncapped	Uncapped %	Capped	Capped %	Differential
India	71,083	21.8%	140,607	47.5%	+69,524 (+97.8%)
China	22,822	7.0%	18,841	6.4%	-3,981 (-17.4%)
Other	172,586	52.9%	92,485	31.2%	-80,101 (-46.4%)
Philippines	32,081	9.8%	29,709	10.0%	-2,372 (-7.4%)
South Korea	14,964	4.6%	13,811	4.7%	-1,153 (-7.7%)
Brazil	12,765	3.9%	697	0.2%	-12,068 (-94.5%)
Total	326,301	100.0%	296,150	100.0%	-30,151 (-9.2%)

Figure 22: Final EB-3 category backlogs after FY2013–FY2035 simulation period. Bars show both principals-only (solid color) and total backlog including dependents (hatched pattern).

The EB-4 backlog is dominated overwhelmingly by “Other” nationality in both scenarios. “Other” comprises 98.5% of capped backlog (460,046 applicants) and 97.3% of uncapped backlog (451,506 applicants). India represents the only other nationality with measurable presence (1.5% capped, 1.7% uncapped), with 7,180 and 7,659 applicants respectively. All other nationalities (China, Philippines, Brazil, and South Korea) maintain zero representation under caps and minimal representation (0.2%–0.3% each) under uncapped allocation.

Table 36: EB-4 Backlog by Nationality

Nationality	Uncapped	Uncapped %	Capped	Capped %	Differential
India	7,659	1.7%	7,180	1.5%	-479 (-6.3%)
China	1,117	0.2%	0	0.0%	-1,117 (-100.0%)
Other	451,506	97.3%	460,046	98.5%	+8,540 (+1.9%)
Philippines	1,324	0.3%	0	0.0%	-1,324 (-100.0%)
South Korea	1,194	0.3%	0	0.0%	-1,194 (-100.0%)
Brazil	1,185	0.3%	0	0.0%	-1,185 (-100.0%)
Total	463,985	100.0%	467,226	100.0%	+3,241 (+0.7%)

Figure 23: Final EB-4 category backlogs after FY2013–FY2035 simulation period. Bars show both principals-only (solid color) and total backlog including dependents (hatched pattern).

The EB-5 backlog is concentrated among Chinese investors in both scenarios. China comprises 87.1% of capped EB-5 backlog (29,788 applicants) and 64.9% of uncapped backlog (22,380 applicants), a differential of 7,408 additional Chinese applicants under caps. India represents the only other nationality with representation under caps (12.9%, 4,393 applicants), while under uncapped allocation, “Other” nationalities comprise 21.9% (7,549 applicants), India 9.8% (3,371 applicants), and South Korea, Brazil, and Philippines together comprise 3.4%.

Table 37: EB-5 Backlog by Nationality

Nationality	Uncapped	Uncapped %	Capped	Capped %	Differential
India	3,371	9.8%	4,393	12.9%	+1,022 (+30.3%)
China	22,380	64.9%	29,788	87.1%	+7,408 (+33.1%)
Other	7,549	21.9%	0	0.0%	-7,549 (-100.0%)
Philippines	26	0.1%	0	0.0%	-26 (-100.0%)
South Korea	762	2.2%	0	0.0%	-762 (-100.0%)
Brazil	371	1.1%	0	0.0%	-371 (-100.0%)
Total	34,459	100.0%	34,181	100.0%	-278 (-0.8%)

Figure 24: Final EB-5 category backlogs after FY2013–FY2035 simulation period. Bars show both principals-only (solid color) and total backlog including dependents (hatched pattern).

5.2.3 Nationality-Specific Backlog Patterns

Aggregate Backlog Distribution Analysis The aggregate backlog distribution across nationalities illustrates the central redistributive effect of per-country caps: they concentrate backlog burden on high-demand nationalities while shifting it away from the low-demand nationalities. Under per-country caps, India accounts for 47.3% of the total backlog (727,440 applicants), compared to just 29.8% under uncapped allocation (469,837 applicants), a net increase of 257,603 Indian applicants (+54.8%).

Conversely, the “Other” nationality category sees its backlog share fall from 54.8% in the uncapped scenario (864,349 applicants) to 39.3% under caps (605,396 applicants), a decline of 258,953 applicants (-30.0%). This nearly one-for-one shift (India +257,603; “Other” -258,953) underscores that per-country caps operate as a zero-sum reallocation mechanism: constraining high-demand nationalities frees visa capacity that is then absorbed by lower-demand groups.

China’s aggregate backlog rises modestly under caps (148,484 vs. 127,490; +20,994 or +16.5%), reflecting China’s participation across multiple EB categories with uneven cap-binding intensity, combined with its relatively high exit rate, which prevents large-scale queue accumulation.

Brazil, South Korea, and the Philippines experience substantial backlog increases in the capped scenario: Brazil rises from 11,153 to 44,511 (+33,358, or 74.9%), South Korea from 17,237 to 34,006 (+16,769, or 49.3%), and the Philippines from 29,709 to 36,006 (+6,297, or 17.5%). This pattern reflects the “fast-track” mechanism embedded in per-country caps: these lower-demand nationalities benefit from reserved visa allocations, allowing applicants to move ahead of the queues for high-demand countries like India and China. In contrast, under uncapped allocation, without nationality-specific bottlenecks to constrain India and China, lower-demand nationalities face more competition for visas and consequently accumulate larger backlogs relative to the capped scenario.

Table 38: Aggregate Backlog Distribution by Nationality

Nationality	Uncapped	Uncapped %	Capped	Capped %	Differential
India	469,837	29.8%	727,440	47.3%	+257,603 (+54.8%)
Other	864,349	54.8%	605,396	39.3%	-258,953 (-30.0%)
China	127,490	8.1%	148,484	9.6%	+20,994 (+16.5%)
Brazil	44,511	2.8%	11,153	0.7%	-33,358 (-74.9%)
South Korea	34,006	2.2%	17,237	1.1%	-16,769 (-49.3%)
Philippines	36,006	2.3%	29,709	1.9%	-6,297 (-17.5%)
Total	1,576,199	100.0%	1,539,419	100.0%	-36,780 (-2.3%)

Figure 25: Final nationality backlogs after FY2013–FY2035 simulation period. Bars show both principals-only (solid color) and total backlog including dependents (hatched pattern).

5.3 Child Age-Out Incidence and Distribution

The simulation’s primary research question, the differential impact of per-country caps on child age-out incidence, produces the study’s most consequential findings.

5.3.1 Aggregate Age-Out Incidence

Over the 23-year simulation period (FY2013–FY2035), the model projects that per-country caps are directly responsible for approximately 59,000 additional children permanently losing derivative beneficiary eligibility over the projection period, a near 17-fold increase in age-out incidence.

Table 39: Aggregate Child Age-Outs (FY2013–FY2035)

Metric	Value
Uncapped Total	3,721
Capped Total	62,764
Differential	+59,043
Factor Increase	16.9×

5.3.2 Temporal Evolution of Age-Out Incidence

Annual age-out incidence remains minimal during FY2013–FY2024 in both scenarios, due to the fact that the simulation initializes a newly-created synthetic backlog in which children of early-filed petitions have not yet reached age 21. However, age-out incidence accelerates sharply under the capped scenario beginning in FY2025 as children from early cohorts approach the 21-year-old threshold while parents remain in extended queues due to per-country cap constraints. The differential between scenarios expands monotonically from +137 children in FY2025 to +14,029 in FY2035, demonstrating that per-country cap constraints produce an escalating burden on dependent children throughout the projection.

Table 40: Annual Age-Out Incidence (FY2025–FY2035)

Fiscal Year	Uncapped	Capped	Differential
2025	19	156	+137
2026	35	397	+362
2027	60	723	+663
2028	106	1,572	+1,466
2029	124	2,546	+2,422
2030	245	4,109	+3,864
2031	293	6,175	+5,882
2032	464	8,347	+7,883
2033	558	10,539	+9,981
2034	794	13,086	+12,292
2035	988	15,017	+14,029

(a) Annual child age-outs

(b) Cumulative child age-outs

Figure 26: Child age-outs over time across uncapped and capped scenarios, FY2013–FY2035.

5.3.3 Nationality Distribution of Age-Outs

The nationality distribution of age-outs reveals that per-country caps concentrate the burden overwhelmingly on Indian beneficiaries. Indian children comprise 98.8% of all age-outs in the capped scenario (62,033 children) compared to only 36.1% in the uncapped scenario (1,342 children).

Table 41: Child Age-Outs by Nationality

Nationality	Uncapped	Capped
India	1,342 (36.1%)	62,033 (98.8%)
Other	1,426 (38.3%)	708 (1.1%)
Brazil	832 (22.4%)	7 (0.01%)
China	77 (2.1%)	15 (0.02%)
South Korea	32 (0.9%)	0 (0.0%)
Philippines	12 (0.3%)	1 (0.00%)

(a) Uncapped scenario

(b) Capped scenario (7% per-country cap)

Figure 27: Nationality proportions of age-outs across uncapped and capped scenarios, FY2013–FY2035.

Figure 28: Nationality counts of age-outs across uncapped and capped scenarios, FY2013–FY2035

5.3.4 EB Category Distribution of Age-Outs

The category distribution of age-outs reveals the concentration to be in EB-2 and EB-3.

EB-2 dominates age-out incidence in both scenarios but exhibits more extreme concentration under the capped scenario. The capped scenario produces 55,899 EB-2 age-outs, compared to 3,042 in the uncapped scenario, a differential of 52,857 additional children. EB-3 contributes a substantial secondary share of capped age-outs (6,134 children), compared to the uncapped scenario (159 children).

The trends in EB-2 and EB-3 (categories predominantly constituted by Indian nationals) demonstrates that per-country caps produce concentrated age-out consequences not merely on a single nationality but within specific employment-based categories dominated by that nationality.

Absolute EB-4 age-outs increase by 209 under caps, but their relative share declines substantially (13.6% uncapped to 1.1% capped) because the massive EB-2/EB-3 increase overwhelms all other categories proportionally.

EB-1 and EB-5 categories contribute negligible age-outs in both scenarios (fewer than 15 combined across all years), showing that virtually all dependent children in those categories obtain green card status derivatively before reaching age 21.

Table 42: Child Age-Outs by EB Category

EB Category	Uncapped	Uncapped %	Capped	Capped %	Differential
EB-2	3,042	81.8%	55,899	89.1%	+52,857
EB-3	159	4.3%	6,134	9.8%	+5,975
EB-4	507	13.6%	716	1.1%	+209
EB-1	4	0.1%	3	0.0%	-1
EB-5	9	0.2%	12	0.0%	+3
Total	3,721	100.0%	62,764	100.0%	+59,043

(a) Uncapped Scenario

(b) Capped scenario (7% per-country cap)

Figure 29: Category proportions of age-outs across uncapped and capped scenarios, FY2013–FY2035.

5.4 Sensitivity Analysis and Robustness

5.4.1 India EB-2 Exit Rate

Given the pivotal role of queue attrition in determining wait times, we test the model’s sensitivity to variations in the queue exit rate for Indian EB-2 applicants, the population driving the majority of age-outs. We vary the calibrated base rate (4.0%) by $\pm 20\%$ (Range: 3.2%–4.8%) to account for uncertainty in return migration behavior.

Results indicate that the core finding, that per-country caps are the primary driver of age-outs, is structurally robust across the parameter space. Under the High Attrition scenario (4.8%), where applicants abandon the queue more

rapidly, the total volume of age-outs declines to 53,772, yet the policy-induced differential remains substantial at 50,772. Conversely, under the Low Attrition scenario (3.2%), the absolute scale of the crisis expands to 73,267 age-outs, with a net differential of 68,537 directly attributable to the cap. In all scenarios, the per-country cap is responsible for over 93% of total projected age-outs, confirming that the policy’s exclusionary effect persists regardless of variations in India’s EB-2 exit rate.

Table 43: Sensitivity Analysis: India EB-2 Exit Rate

Scenario	India EB-2 Exit Rate	Uncapped Age-Outs	Capped Age-Outs	Differential
Low Attrition	3.2%	4,730	73,267	68,537
Base Case	4.0%	3,721	62,764	59,043
High Attrition	4.8%	3,000	53,772	50,772

5.4.2 India Child per Worker

The absolute volume of age-outs is partly a function of the number of dependent children accompanying each principal applicant. To assess the influence of our demographic calibration (1.02 children per Indian worker), we re-ran the simulation under Low Fertility (0.92) and High Fertility (1.12) scenarios for the Indian applicant pool.

Results indicate that our core finding, that per-country caps are the primary driver of age-outs, is structurally robust across demographic variations. Under the High Fertility scenario, the total volume of age-outs rises to 70,495 simply because more children are in the queue, yet the policy-induced differential (66,218) scales in near-perfect proportion. Conversely, under the Low Fertility scenario, the absolute scale of the crisis declines to 50,888, but the cap continues to generate nearly 48,000 excess age-outs. In all scenarios, the per-country cap accounts for over 93% of total projected age-outs, confirming that the per-country cap contributes to intergenerational exclusion regardless of variation in fertility inputs.

Table 44: Sensitivity Analysis: India Children Per Worker

Scenario	India Children/Worker	Uncapped	Capped	Differential
Low Fertility	0.92	3,030	50,888	47,858
Base Case	1.02	3,721	62,764	59,043
High Fertility	1.12	4,277	70,495	66,218

5.4.3 Average Age

Our baseline model adopts a conservative assumption (mean child entry age of 1.03 years for India). To test the sensitivity of our findings, we simulated “Toddler Cohort” (Mean Age of 3.0) and “School-Age Cohort” (Mean Age of 6.0) scenarios.

Under the School-Age Cohort scenario, which represents families arriving with six-year-olds, the total number of age-outs nearly triples to 211,174, while the policy-induced differential expands to 164,727. In the more modest Toddler Cohort scenario (Mean Age = 3.0), total age-outs surge to 111,807, representing a 78% increase over the baseline. This sensitivity confirms that even small upward shifts in the entry age of dependent children disproportionately accelerate protection failures within the backlog.

These findings suggest that under current statutory constraints, Indian beneficiaries face an exceptionally high risk of family separation, unless the principal’s priority date is established during their children’s infancy.

Table 45: Sensitivity Analysis: Mean Entry Age (India)

Scenario	Mean Entry Age	Uncapped	Capped	Differential
Base Case	1.03 Years	3,721	62,764	59,043
Toddler Cohort	3.0 Years	9,402	111,807	102,405
School-Age Cohort	6.0 Years	46,447	211,174	164,727

5.4.4 Years Before Queue Entry

Our baseline model assumes immigrants enter an EB visa queue 3 years after arrival. However, many families face extended delays before filing a petition. To assess how these administrative “pre-queues” interact with the statutory backlog, we tested scenarios where the pre-filing delay is shortened (2 Years) or extended (4 Years).

Under the Extended Delay scenario, total age-outs surge to 86,465, confirming that the safety margin for dependent children is extremely fragile. Functionally, this parameter tests the same biological constraint as the child-age sensitivity, where any reduction in the eligibility window accelerates protection failures. Conversely, the Short Delay scenario reveals that even expedited pre-petition processing leaves the structural bottleneck intact, with 43,534 total age-outs.

Table 46: Sensitivity Analysis: Wait Before Queue Entry

Scenario	Pre-Queue Wait	Uncapped	Capped	Differential
Short Delay	2 Years	1,676	43,534	41,858
Base Case	3 Years	3,721	62,764	59,043
Extended Delay	4 Years	7,876	86,465	78,589

5.5 Limitations

Synthetic Backlog Initialization The simulation reconstructs the employment-based visa backlog from administrative data spanning FY2013–FY2024. However, the actual USCIS queue predates FY2013. By initializing the synthetic backlog in FY2013 rather than capturing pre-2013 applicants, the model omits historical depth that would have characterized the early simulation years.

This initialization constraint affects early-period dynamics, as the synthetic backlog inherently underestimates historical queue depth, necessitating calibration parameters (specifically exit rates) that are likely lower than empirical reality to match observed backlog sizes. While this calibration successfully aligns the simulation with the June 2025 administrative backlog (+0.5% accuracy), the trajectory during the FY2013–FY2024 transition period may exhibit distortion. Furthermore, for forward-looking projections based on FY2024 parameters, this initialization method creates upward pressure on estimated backlog growth.

Nationality Distribution Assumptions for EB-4 and EB-5 Comprehensive historical nationality distributions for EB-4 and EB-5 filings are not readily available. To address the gap, the model applies FY2024 nationality distributions retrospectively across the FY2013–FY2024 period for both EB-4 and EB-5. This approach introduces two potential biases: it may overrepresent nationalities with rising EB-4 or EB-5 demand in recent years, while underrepresenting nationalities that historically had higher demand.

Although this assumption influences the composition of the EB-4 and EB-5 backlogs, its effect on the model’s primary findings is limited. Age-out outcomes are driven predominantly by EB-2 applicants, whose nationality distributions are empirically grounded across the entire FY2013–FY2024 period, ensuring the robustness of the main analysis.

EB-4 "Other" Nationality Distribution Based on R-1 Visa Issuance Proxy EB-4 encompasses multiple visa subclasses with distinct occupational and nationality profiles, including Special Immigrant Juvenile Status (SIJS), religious workers (R-1), and others. Because USCIS does not disaggregate EB-4 petition filing data by nationality, the model estimates the nationality distribution of non-SIJS EB-4 filings using the nationality distribution of R-1 visas issued in FY2024.

The R-1 category is used as a proxy because it represents a substantial share of EB-4 conversions and has publicly available nationality data. This approach introduces measurement error, as not all R-1 visa holders subsequently file EB-4 petitions.

Consequently, assuming that R-1 issuance nationality distributions approximate EB-4 filing distributions (excluding SIJS) may bias the model toward nationalities with high R-1 utilization. As with the previous limitation, this assumption affects EB-4 backlog composition, but its impact on the model’s primary findings is limited, since age-out outcomes are driven primarily by EB-2 applicants.

EB-5 Nationality Distribution Based on Issuance Data The model calibrates EB-5 nationality distributions using FY2024 issuance data rather than I-526 petition filings, because USCIS does not publicly release petition-level nationality distributions for EB-5 investor petitions.

Since issuances, unlike petitions, are subject to the 7% per-country cap, this approach likely underestimates the share of applicants from capped countries while overestimating the share from non-capped countries. Nevertheless, this limitation has minimal impact on the study's conclusions, as EB-5 accounts for a negligible share of estimated child age-outs.

Uniform Delay Before Queue Entry The model assumes a uniform three-year administrative delay between arrival and queue entry for all applicants. In reality, this interval varies widely: some beneficiaries enter the queue immediately upon arrival, while others experience longer delays.

Although this simplification affects the biological runway of dependent children, sensitivity analyses find that results remain robust regardless of pre-queue delay assumptions.

6 Conclusion

6.1 Summary of Findings

This study presents the first dynamic microsimulation of age-out incidence in the U.S. employment-based immigration system and directly addresses the three empirical questions posed in the introduction: (1) the aggregate difference in child age-outs between capped and uncapped regimes; (2) the effect of the per-country cap on the nationality distribution of the backlog; and (3) the extent to which risks of family separation concentrate within specific preference categories and nationalities. The model reconstructs the petitioner-level queue from FY2013 through FY2024 and projects outcomes through FY2035 under both the current capped regime and an uncapped counterfactual.

Under the uncapped regime, 3,721 dependent children age out of eligibility; under the capped regime, 62,764 age out. This difference of 59,043 represents a 16.9-fold increase. The magnitude of the differential remains stable across sensitivity analyses that vary exit rates, fertility rates, child entry age, and pre-filing administrative delays.

Indian nationals account for 98.8% of age-outs under the capped scenario (61,940 of 62,764), compared with 36.1% in the uncapped scenario (1,344 of 3,721). The capped system therefore produces an extreme concentration of age-out risk among Indian applicants relative to the uncapped baseline. The cap also reshapes the nationality composition of the backlog. India's share of total principals increases from 29.8% in the uncapped scenario to 47.3% in the capped scenario, while the share of "Other" nationalities falls from 54.8% to 39.3%.

Age-outs are heavily concentrated in preference categories where the cap is most restrictive. In the capped scenario, EB-2 accounts for 89.1% of all age-outs, EB-3 accounts for 9.8%, and the combined contribution of EB-1, EB-4, and EB-5 is 1.1%. The uncapped scenario exhibits similar ordering but with meaningfully less concentration (EB-2: 81.8%, EB-3: 4.3%).

Across both scenarios, total visa utilization remains effectively identical at 3.79 million visas over the projection period. The per-country cap's effect is therefore derived from its distributive effects: by reallocating a fixed number of visas across nationalities, the cap lengthens queues for high-demand countries and shortens them for others. Age-out incidence emerges directly from this redistribution, as longer queues for certain nationalities push more dependent children past the statutory age threshold, even though the total number of visas issued is unchanged.

6.2 Implications for Future Research

This analysis establishes baseline mechanics of age-out incidence under current statutory design. Three extensions are especially promising.

Future Research Direction 1: Behavioral Responses and Migrant Selection Multi-decade backlogs can potentially alter the self-selection of future high-skilled migrants. Future research could investigate how the prospect of family separation influences the decision-making of prospective high-skilled migrants. Specifically, does the "age-out penalty" deter mid-career professionals (who have children) from entering the U.S. labor market, thereby altering the human capital composition of the U.S. labor force?

Future Research Direction 2: Policy Reform Simulation The study compares only two scenarios: current policy (7% per-country cap) and uncapped FIFO. Future research could simulate intermediate reforms: increased per-country caps (e.g., 10%, 15%, 20%), nationality-specific caps based on demand, increased aggregate visa caps, or age-prioritized allocation schemes. Systematic comparison of reform options would provide a quantitative basis for policy debates. Luckily, the current model makes this exceptionally easy as it only requires the change of a single parameter (the 7% per-country cap).

Future Research Direction 3: Longitudinal Trajectories of the "Aged-Out" Cohort This study quantifies the incidence of aging out, but the outcomes for these individuals remain under-studied. Future research could employ longitudinal tracking to determine the actual pathways taken by aged-out children. What proportion successfully transition to F-1/H-1B status versus emigrating? Do those who remain in the U.S. experience an “assimilation penalty” (e.g., lower wages, delayed career progression) due to the reset of their immigration status or barriers experienced along the way? Understanding these life-course trajectories is essential for assessing the full social cost of the policy.

6.3 Conflict of Interest

The author declares no competing interests.

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